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First progress report on science - stakeholder
Interaction

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1. Introduction

EU-PolarNet has a clear mandate to co-design an integrated European Polar Research Programme together with different stakeholders from the beginning of the creation process. By that, it shall guarantee that the research programme will generate tangible benefits for society. Work Package 4 of the project (Interaction with Stakeholders and end-users) has identified stakeholders (deliverable 4.5) related to the polar regions and the generated stakeholder map has been used to reinforce the interactions and promote stakeholder participation in different surveys and events. EU-PolarNet has been actively searching for interaction with stakeholders and various possibilities of engagement have been used, promoting participation at established events, such as the Arctic Circle Assembly; SCAR Conferences and Arctic Frontiers, and organizing several stand-alone events.

2. Past and ongoing stakeholder interaction activities

The stakeholder related events organized by EU-PolarNet cover different categories. In most cases, the interaction took place within the framework of larger events, where EU-PolarNet organized breakout sessions or side events. On other occasions, EU-PolarNet organized special events targeted at particular stakeholder groups. EU-PolarNet has used a wide range of opportunities available to interact with stakeholders, including **Town Hall meetings** at European institutions or at large conferences (i.e. AGU, SCAR), **policy briefings** with European and national policy makers in Brussels, **stakeholder meetings**, workshops and sessions during polar conferences (e.g. Arctic Circle, Adaptation Futures, ICASS IX), or **side events** during international climate conferences (such as COP21, COP22 and COP23). One major effort was a public online stakeholder **consultation**, in which the opinion of over 500 stakeholders were obtained and analyzed, identifying the research priorities for peoples and institutions living, working or having research interest in the polar regions. A particularly intensive transdisciplinary interaction was marked by the **White Paper Workshop** held near Madrid (Spain), in which 50 participants were invited to develop ideas for a set of polar White Papers. Participants from funding agencies, business, indigenous peoples, infrastructure operators and research were working closely together during this five day workshop.

2.1 Examples of the activities

a) Stakeholder Survey

EU-PolarNet conducted a stakeholder engagement survey at three events (the EU-PolarNet Town Hall Event 2016 in Brussels, the Arctic Circle 2016 in Reykjavik, and the WOC Sustainable Ocean Summit 2016 in Rotterdam), where printed surveys were handed out to all participants. The same survey was published on the EU-PolarNet website alongside an online survey on polar priorities in April 2017, of which the stakeholder survey is still available today. Most replies (263 out of 302) were received through the online survey.

In the survey, participants were asked about their motivation for engaging in research projects, the stage of a research project they wanted to get involved in and how they were best involved in a research project. These three questions offered multi-choice options, which aimed at covering key areas of motivation (such as staying informed, receiving information for policy making and defining research questions), stages of engagement (from project planning to dissemination) and modes of engagement (such as meetings, workshops and personal dialogues) respectively.

It gives valuable insights to how stakeholders would like to get engaged in research projects and builds the basis for future efforts in targeting engagement activities to specific stakeholder groups. The results for example suggest that academic stakeholders are keen to participate from the problem definition to the dissemination of the final results, whereas many non-academic stakeholders preferred getting involved in the dissemination of results and in putting these in use for informed decision-making.

b) Stakeholder workshops

Three stakeholder workshops were organized covering the following themes: health and well-being, Arctic ecosystems and ecosystem services, and climate-related effects on the Arctic cryosphere and adaptation options. These half-day workshops were held in conjunction with large polar conferences and built upon the input from sessions held during the respective conference. During the workshops scientific experts from a wide range to social and natural science disciplines from Europe and North America, representatives from indigenous peoples, local communities and practitioners discussed stakeholder relevant research needs, which will be incorporated in the integrated European polar research programme.

c) Online stakeholder consultation

An online stakeholder survey was designed to feed into the white paper process. The survey aimed at giving stakeholders a chance to state where they saw challenges and opportunities arising in the Polar Regions (especially in the region where they lived or worked in), which should be solved by future research. The survey was conducted during the spring - early summer 2017 and personalized emails in English, Swedish, Norwegian, Finnish, Russian, German, Spanish, and Portuguese were sent to over 1000 individuals either living or doing research in polar regions. In addition the link to the survey was published widely in the social media and web sites.

The survey comprised a short list of demographic questions, including the area of residence, nationality and gender and one main question:

What are the most important topics in relation to your work and/or everyday life (either locally, nationally or internationally) in the Polar Regions that should be solved by future research?

Respondents were able to list three topics, which were also asked to be categorized under one of the five overarching themes:

- People and societal issues
- Climate and cryosphere (such as sea ice, glaciers, ice sheets and permafrost)
- Sustainable resources and human impact
- Polar biology, ecology and biodiversity
- New technology

The survey was held in English. However, respondents were able to answer in their national language if preferred.

Over 500 answers received were clustered by the themes and topics and prior to the White Paper Workshop the experts taking part to the Workshop voted the most important ones to be developed further in the workshop.

d) White Paper Workshop

The white paper workshop had the purpose of developing the ideas and structure of a number of white papers about the different research needs on 5 different themes: polar biology, climate and cryosphere, technology, people and societal issues, as well as sustainable resources and human impact. The workshop involved stakeholders from different sectors including science, business, indigenous peoples, administrations, etc. Jointly the participants identified main research needs of societal relevance within the five overarching themes, which should be addressed by future research. The research needs were based on the results from a public online survey (see c. The writing of these five white papers is still in process and will be finished in next months).

e) Side Events at the UN Climate Conference COP23

EU-PolarNet was co-organiser of three polar side events at the COP23, which was organised by Fiji and took place in Bonn, Germany:

- Arctic States and Small Island States: Two regions inextricably linked through climate change; organized by EU-PolarNet, ICE-ARC, Deutsche Gesellschaft fuer Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ), the Alfred Wegener Institute and the British Antarctic Survey. This session provided an opportunity for influential leaders to demonstrate the dramatic climate driven changes that are occurring in the fundamentally different regions – the Arctic and Small Island Developing States – explain why the international community must increase the ambition of its mitigation and adaptation efforts, and provide their vision for outcome of the COP23.
- Adaptation Now! But how? How climate research in the polar regions is influencing adaptation strategies for Small Island States; organized by EU-PolarNet, ICE-ARC, Deutsche Gesellschaft fuer Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ), the Alfred Wegener Institute and the British Antarctic Survey. This side-event provided an excellent opportunity to better understand the adaptation challenges and the possible financing mechanisms required to support resilience building and adaptation (or even migration) processes. By bringing together science, policy and society we learned more about the triggers of global sea-level rise and the impacts especially on Arctic and Small Island Developing States.
- Polar insights for climate action: Arctic science contributions to implementing the Paris Agreement, co-organised by the EU Arctic Cluster. This session provided up-to-date and policy-relevant information on Arctic change and its global implications, including thawing permafrost, the contribution of melting glaciers and ice sheets on the global sea level, the influence of the Arctic on the global oceans, and changing weather patterns.

f) Town Hall Event in Brussels

Themed “Towards the 1.5°C climate goal – Perspectives from the Polar Regions” the EU-PolarNet Townhall Event’s objective, which was held on 27th September 2016 in the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences in Brussels, was to explore how future polar research projects can contribute to limiting global warming to a worldwide average of 1.5°C – while bringing tangible benefits to the European society. To consider the wide range of interests and needs, EU-PolarNet brought together polar science experts with policy makers, industry and NGO representatives, as well as local and indigenous communities. In total around 110 people participated at this full-day event. Keynote addresses and high-level expert panels set the scene for thought-provoking discussions focussed on what European society needs from polar research and what Europe’s priorities for polar research should be.

2.2 Evaluation of stakeholder interaction

The consortium has invested much time and effort in interacting with stakeholders, over 10 events per year, from different stakeholder group. The maximum number of events was held in fall-2017 when 5 interactions were organized in only three months (figure 1). This demonstrates that the consortium is fully aware of the relevance of this point and makes great investment of time and resources to cover this aspect.

Figure 1. Frequency of events per season.

During those interaction opportunities, EU-PolarNet was able to engage with a considerable amount of people (figure 2).

Figure 2. Estimated number of people reached by interaction activity.

Although categorizing the audiences reached is not an easy task, because frequently participants build a heterogeneous group, most of the EU-PolarNet stakeholder related events reached audiences referred to sciences, with a good balance between researchers OR research organisations OR projects on natural and social sciences (figure 3). Groups related with policy, and NGOs or international organizations were also well covered with over 10 events each. Industry participated in several events, covering tourism, shipping, fisheries, energy and technology). Indigenous communities and media also interacted with EU-PolarNet but on fewer occasions.

Figure 3. Distribution of events targeted at specific stakeholder groups.

Of the 30 events organized (see the complete list in Annex I) with stakeholders from March 2015 until September 2017, 60% were targeted at Arctic topics, whereas only 7% were related to only Antarctic topics and 33% can be considered related to topics on both poles (figure 4).

Figure 4. Distribution of events targeted at Arctic or Antarctic issues or issues relevant for both Polar Regions.

Looking at the overall thematic focus of the stakeholder interactions, one can see that many interactions focused on introducing EU-PolarNet and gain visibility for the project (figure 5). This hold

especially true for the initial phase of the project, where awareness rising was a priority. Further reoccurring themes were climate change and adaptation. EU-PolarNet also organized three interactive workshops that specifically looked at how to improve stakeholder engagement.

Figure 5. Distribution of thematic focus of interaction activity.

3. Interaction map

In terms of the geographical distribution of the events, Figure 3 shows that most events took place in Europe (73%), but other locations in Africa, America and Asia have also hosted EU-PolarNet events. In terms of international visibility and policy relevance, EU-PolarNet's side events during COP21, COP22 and COP23 can be highlighted. The conferences brought together 40.000 participants from almost 200 countries. Due to the geographical distribution of the organized events and the international perspective of most of them, it can be stated that EU-PolarNet has had in this period of time a wide distribution, trying to reaching stakeholders all over the world.

Figure 6. Geographical distribution of the EU-PolarNet events. The size of the dots is proportional to the number of events

4. Future perspectives

The EU-PolarNet consortium can look back at a wide range of stakeholder interactions. However, the consortium has also identified some aspects that can be improved and some stakeholder groups that should have been engaged more frequently. This will be a task for the remaining project lifespan. Although indigenous communities have been reached at several forums, more effort should be put into incorporating indigenous peoples and local community's knowledge in the EU-PolarNet research planning process. This is not an easy task because relationships are built up upon trust over long time periods. However, EU-PolarNet is aware of these problems and is increasing its efforts to work with indigenous and local communities. The two indigenous colleagues (a Saami representative and an Inuit representative from Greenland) that were invited, accepted and actively contributed to the white paper process, which can be seen as a first success and demonstrates that established personal contacts are key for lasting and trustful partnerships. EU-PolarNet is also aiming include indigenous representatives in the design of the Integrated Polar Research Programme.

We also consider that links with education and capacity building structures should be implemented, since the education is the basis for knowledge and interaction. This could be reinforced through the contacts that members of EU-PolarNet have with educational programmes such as APECS and, UArctic.

Industry is well represented among the stakeholders participating in the events, but several sectors of industry have not been addressed by EU-PolarNet yet. In particular, the companies involved in polar research operations (e.g. Kings Bay in the Arctic, or AGUNSA in the Antarctic) might be interested in participating in the co-production process of the integrated European Polar Research programme.

Another important group of stakeholders are non-governmental organisations that are very active in the polar regions and represent the civil society. We are aware that NGOs such as WWF and Greenpeace could feed in relevant contributions to the research programme and that we need to make efforts in cooperating closer with them.

Although funding agencies, as well as the European Commission, have been involved frequently in the events organized by EU-PolarNet, this is an especially relevant group of stakeholders which should be approached continuously. This interaction might be reinforced, mainly in non-Arctic countries, and

personal interactions, webinars or other dissemination tools should be used to inform more high level persons from European funding agencies. EU-PolarNet considers the interaction with high level international polar organizations important, such as the Antarctic Treaty System and the Arctic Council, to obtain crucial political and operational information and benefiting from expertise exchange with members of these organizations.

EU-PolarNet is moreover working towards merging stakeholder efforts with other EU funded Arctic projects, working together in the network of the EU Arctic Cluster. By cooperating more closely between these projects and creating synergies, investments can be made more efficiently, by avoiding duplication, and the risk of stakeholder fatigue will be limited, as stakeholders are not approached by all individual projects.

